

CONDENSATION OF ALDEHYDES WITH MALONIC ACID. PART XXVI.
CONDENSATION OF DIHYDROCINNAMALDEHYDE

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Dihydrocinnamaldehyde has been condensed with malonic acid under different conditions. In the presence of pyridine or piperidine, γ -benzylcrotonic acid is obtained, the yield of which under certain conditions goes up to about 55%. In the absence of any condensing agent, as well as under other conditions, the dibasic dihydrocinnamylidene-malonic acid is obtained, the yield of which in a pure form does not exceed 25%. It has not been described before in literature.

Dihydrocinnamic aldehyde has not been condensed with Perkin's reagents, or with malonic acid outside this laboratory. Kurien and Pandya (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 825) condensed it with malonic acid in the presence of pyridine (0.15 mol.) by heating it on a water-bath for 4 hours and reported a yield of 29% of γ -benzylcrotonic acid.

This aldehyde is of particular interest as it may be looked upon as being more aliphatic than its close relative, cinnamaldehyde: for, though both have a common phenyl group, that group is connected in cinnamaldehyde by means of a conjugated double bond system, even beyond the benzene ring, with the aldehyde group; but in dihydrocinnamaldehyde this last double bond outside the ring disappears and the reactivity of the aldehyde group is now found to be considerably impaired. Thus cinnamaldehyde, like most of the other benzaldehyde-derived aromatic aldehydes, condenses easily with malonic acid, giving a 96% yield of cinnamylidene-malonic acid and 61% yield of the corresponding monobasic cinnamylidene-acetic acid (Gupta and Pandya, *ibid.*, 1947, 24, 445). Dihydrocinnamaldehyde, on the other hand, has been so slow to combine that it gives about 25% yield of the dibasic acid and not more than 55% yield of the monobasic acid.

Of the many condensation experiments made in this laboratory, only a few typical ones are described in this paper. The monobasic acid came out in the presence of either piperidine or pyridine. The dibasic acid was obtained under a variety of conditions, such as in ether, in glacial acetic acid, in the absence of any solvent or of any condensing agent, or with fairly long heating on the water-bath. It was a yellow substance melting at 198-99°.

The dibasic acid, $C_6H_5.CH_2CH_2CH : C(COOH)_2$, is claimed to have been prepared by Thiele and Meisenheimer (*Annalen*, 1899, 306, 260; cf. Beilstein, Band IX, 1926, p. 905) and is reported as δ -phenyl- α -butylene $\alpha\alpha$ -dicarboxylic acid. They heated the isomeric δ -phenyl- β -butylene- $\alpha\alpha$ -dicarboxylic acid (m. p. 106-108°, decomp.) on a water-bath with caustic soda for a long time, but their product melted at a low temperature, 115-16°. Ruber (*Ber.*, 1904, 37, 3123) seems to have prepared the same acid by keeping the isomeric acid with fuming sulphuric acid at room temperature for one month and his product had a slightly higher melting point, 124°. Both the workers depended on a shift of the double bond under rather drastic conditions, but there is no evidence

that the reaction had completed itself or that the product was not a mixture of the two isomers. On the other hand, the purity of the product in the condensation in the presence of pyridine, particularly in aliphatic aldehydes, is evident (Harding and Weizmann, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 97, 299; vide also Beilstein, 1926, Band IX, p. 905). It is equally true that, as Boxer and Linstead (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1877, 31, 738) have pointed out, the condensation of the aliphatic aldehydes gives on the whole a much smaller yield.

EXPERIMENTAL

γ-Benzylcrotonic Acid.—Dihydrocinnamaldehyde (1.34 g.), malonic acid (1.034 g.) and pyridine (0.13 c.c.) (1:1:0.15 mol.) were heated on a water-bath for 11 hours. A semi-solid mass that appeared next morning was taken out as usual; a milky white precipitate was obtained, melting at 101°, and, after recrystallisation (alcohol), melting finally at 103.5-104°. It agrees with the melting point 104° given in literature (Fittig and Hoffmann, *Annalen*, 1894, 288, 304; vide, Beilstein, 1926, Band IX, p. 621). (Found: Equiv., 177.5; benzylcrotonic acid, C₁₁H₁₂O₂ requires equiv., 176). The yield of the pure acid was 13.8%.

In 1:1:1 mol. proportions, the same materials gave 18.5% yield, and heating at 120°-130° for 7 to 8 hours gave 21% yield. With piperidine (3 drops) instead of pyridine, and 8 hours' heating at 110°-120°, the yield was a little less, 18.8%.

Heating at 180° for about 2 hours gave the mono-acid in the highest yield, namely 55%.

Dihydrocinnamylidene-malonic Acid.—The aldehyde and the malonic acid were heated alone on a water-bath for 5 hours; the mass fused in 2 hours and then became pink, solidifying gradually again after 4 hours. After the usual treatment a yellowish product was obtained, m. p. 192.5-193.5° (effervescence). After several recrystallisations the final melting point was 198-99° (effervescence). (Found: Equiv., 110.88; dihydrocinnamylidene-malonic acid, C₁₂H₁₁O₄ requires equiv., 110; the mono-acid requires equiv., 176). The yield of the dibasic acid was 15.8%.

The acid is soluble in alcohol, chloroform, acetone and benzene, less in ether, still less in water and in glacial acetic acid. It decolorises Bayer's reagent and bromine water.

Heating for 7 hours, instead of 5, raised the yield to 20%, while a higher temperature, 110°-115° (6 hours) gave 22% yield. Still higher temperatures or longer heatings decomposed the dibasic acid to the monobasic and gave mixtures of the two acids; thus 13 hours' heating on a water-bath gave a product melting at 179°. Ten hours' heating on a water-bath gave, however, pure dibasic acid in 25% yield. Heating with glacial acetic acid (Stuart, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1888, 58, 142) or with ether gave very poor yields of the dibasic acid.

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